

***Gazania krebsiana*
subsp. *krebsiana***
Gousblom

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Group: Eudicot

Size: 25 cm (height).

Distribution:

The species is distributed throughout most provinces of South Africa, excluding the northernmost provinces, and is also found in Lesotho. It occurs in the Fynbos, Succulent Karoo, Nama-Karoo, and Grassland biomes.

Importance:

The subspecies is endemic to South Africa and Lesotho and is a parent of the spectacular hybrids grown commercially as ornamentals worldwide. It is a common and conspicuous component of the Fynbos, Succulent Karoo, and Nama-Karoo floras. The availability of genomic information will facilitate molecular breeding of novel ornamental hybrid strains, gene mining, and the potential utilisation of bioactive compounds.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 57.54 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 14.61 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm
Genome Length: 2.22 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 8.0%, Duplicated: 91.8%]
BUSCO database: viridiplantae
Assembly N50: 7 376.8 kilobases
Contig number: 1 612

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